

Complexes of 3,4-Dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine with some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} metal ions with 3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine(L) have been synthesised. Their structural features have been investigated on the basis of elemental analyses, electronic and infrared spectral data. The ligand field parameters Dq, B' and β are calculated for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. The ir spectra of the complexes reveal both bidentate and monodentate nature of the ligand. The insolubility in common organic solvents and electronic spectra suggest the polymeric octahedral geometry for Ni^{II}, and distorted octahedral structure for Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. An octahedral polymeric structure may be proposed for Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes.

BENZOFURO[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines are associated with potent pharmacological properties¹. Some compounds have been reported to possess antiinflammatory activity almost as potent as that of aspirin². The literature survey reveals that the reports on complexes of benzofurans and benzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines are scanty^{3,4}. In continuation of our work⁵ on the complexes of 4-substituted-benzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidines, we report in the present communication the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of 3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} metal ions.

Experimental

The ligand 3,4-dihydro-4-oxobenzofuro[3,2-*d*]pyrimidine was synthesised by the known procedure⁶. The complexes were prepared by treating the metal chloride in minimum quantity of hot water with concentrated hot solution of the ligand in DMF in 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) molar ratio for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. The reaction mixture was heated on hot plate and solid sodium acetate was added to facilitate the complexation. Heating was continued with magnetic stirring for 1-2 h during which the solution was concentrated. An oily mass obtained was cooled and treated with solvent ether to get the complex separated. In the case of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes, an aqueous solution of the metal chloride was treated with a hot solution of ligand in DMF in 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) molar ratio, the reaction mixture was then stirred on a hot plate for about 2 h and at room temperature, the complexes were separated on rubbing the walls of the container. The solid complexes thus obtained were filtered, washed and dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride.

The details of elemental analyses and measurements of molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility

and infrared spectra are as described in our previous report⁵. The electronic spectra were recorded in nujol and in DMF in the range 1500-300 and 900-340 nm on DMR-21 and Elico CL-24 spectrophotometers, respectively.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes have high melting points, and are soluble in DMF and DMSO and sparingly soluble or insoluble in common organic solvents, like ethanol, nitro benzene, acetone *etc.* The analytical results (Table 1) suggest 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes and rest of the complexes are in 1 : 2 stoichiometry.

The molar conductances in DMF of all the complexes except Ni^{II} complex are in the range 1.35-28.2 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (Table 1), suggesting them to be non-electrolytes. The NiLCl₂ has an appreciable molar conductance suggesting it to be a 1 : 1 electrolyte⁷.

Magnetic behaviour : The observed magnetic moment value for Co^{II} complex falls in the range 4.7-5.1 B.M., expected for high-spin octahedral complex. The μ_{eff} value of Ni^{II} complex is well within the range expected for hexacoordinated Ni^{II} complex with $t_{2g}^6 e_g^2$ configuration, and for Cu^{II} complex the μ_{eff} observed is 1.62 B.M. which is indicative of one unpaired electron⁸. However, the low value observed for the Cu^{II} complex may be due to magnetic exchange interaction and suggests a polymeric structure for this complex⁹.

Electronic spectra : The solid state electronic spectrum (nujol) of Co^{II} complex is a typical of an octahedral symmetry, exhibiting a broad and weak band at 8333 cm^{-1} and a medium strong band at 19230 cm^{-1} , assignable to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_2) transitions, respectively¹⁰. The

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)			Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.
		M	N	Cl		
CoLCl ₂ ·H ₂ O	260	17.49 (17.64)	8.42 (8.88)	21.11 (21.26)	11.39	4.7
NiLCl ₂	300	18.66 (18.59)	8.93 (8.87)	22.54 (22.49)	88.40	3.2
CuLCl ₂	300	20.21 (19.81)	8.56 (8.74)	22.51 (22.15)	14.02	1.62
ZnL ₂ Cl ₂	280	12.57 (12.86)	11.26 (11.01)	13.78 (11.96)	1.35	—
CdL ₂ Cl ₂	300	20.30 (20.24)	10.28 (10.08)	12.56 (12.78)	28.20	—
HgL ₂ Cl ₂	300	31.30 (31.17)	8.56 (8.70)	11.27 (11.03)	19.52	—

 TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF Co^{II}, Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Complex	Band maxima cm ⁻¹	Assignment	Dq cm ⁻¹	B' cm ⁻¹	β	β° %	ν_2/ν_1	LFSE kcal mol ⁻¹
CoLCl ₂ ·H ₂ O	ν_1 8333 ν_2 17783* ν_3 19230 30770	⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F) ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ A _{2g} (F) ⁴ T _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) Charge transfer	945	801	0.83	17.16	2.13	16.2
NiLCl ₂	ν_1 8772 ν_2 15040 14450* ν_3 25000	³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{2g} (F) ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (F) ³ A _{2g} → ³ T _{1g} (P)	877	876	0.83	17.04	1.70	30.07
CuLCl ₂	16130 33000	³ B _{1g} → ³ A _{1g} ³ B _{1g} → ³ B _{2g} ³ B _{1g} → ³ E _g Charge transfer	1613	—	—	—	—	27.65

* Calculated value

ν_2 band corresponding to the transition ⁴T_{1g}→⁴A_{2g} (F) could not be seen because of its weakness and proximity to a strong ν_3 transition¹¹. However, it can be computed ($\nu_2 = \nu_1 + 10Dq$), which is close to the observed ν_2 band. The ligand field parameters, such as Dq, B', β and LFSE calculated¹² from the assigned band positions of ν_1 and ν_2 (Table 2) depict that the Co^{II} ion is in a distorted octahedral environment. The ratio ν_2/ν_1 2.13 is well within the expected value for distorted octahedral geometry. Further, this configuration is supported by the colour of the complex (light pink) and its magnetic moment data. The pink coloured complex dissolves in DMF forming a light blue solution which may probably be due to the change in geometry¹³. The solid pink coloured complex was recovered on evaporation of solution.

The solid state electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex exhibits two broad bands ν_1 and ν_2 at 8772 and 15040 cm⁻¹, respectively. The third band ν_3 appears as a shoulder around 25000 cm⁻¹ on the sharply rising uv absorption tail of the charge transfer band. This reveals the complex to be an octahedral species¹¹. The values of ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 bands are used calculation of Racah parameter B' and to verify the ν_2 band observed¹⁴. The calculated and experimental values (Table 2) of the middle band

may be proposed as confirmatory evidence for existence of octahedral geometry. The Racah parameter B' (876 cm⁻¹) is less than the free-ion value (1040 cm⁻¹) suggesting a considerable orbital overlap and delocalisation of electrons on the metal ion. The ratio ν_2/ν_1 1.7, is well within the expected value (1.64-1.8)⁹. The electronic spectrum of Ni^{II} complex in DMF shows two bands at 13986 ($\epsilon = 32$), 25641 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon = 156$) assignable to ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g} (F) (ν_2) and ³A_{2g}→³T_{1g} (P) (ν_3) transitions, respectively¹⁵. The third band ν_1 due to ³A_{2g}→³T_{2g} (F) transition could not be located due to the instrumental limitation. However, the energy of ν_1 band has been calculated theoretically¹⁶. It is evident from the comparison of the solid and solution spectra that the complex has the same stereochemistry.

The solid state electronic spectrum of Cu^{II} complex exhibits a single broad asymmetric band with the maximum at 16130 cm⁻¹. This may originate due to the proximity of ³B_{1g}→³A_{1g} (ν_1), ³B_{1g}→³B_{2g} (ν_2) and ³B_{1g}→³E_g (ν_3) transitions, producing a distorted octahedral environment around the metal ion¹⁷. The solution (DMF) spectra of the complex also exhibits a broad asymmetric band in the region 13300-16670 with a maximum at 15620 cm⁻¹ suggesting similar geometry in solution too¹⁸.

Infrared spectra : In the ir spectrum of the Co^{II} complex a medium broad band is observed in the region $3500\text{-}3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to OH stretch of hydrated water molecule. A weighed sample of this complex on drying in oven at $\sim 110^\circ$ loses a water molecule suggesting the presence of lattice held water and not coordinated¹⁹.

The ligand bands observed at 3200 and 3080 cm^{-1} are assigned to NH stretching mode (cyclic amide)²⁰. In all the complexes these bands appear at higher region or remain undisturbed suggesting the non-involvement of NH group in coordination. A strong intense ligand band observed at 1720 cm^{-1} is assigned to C=O (pyrimidone ring) stretch²¹. On complex formation this band shows a negative shift of about 40 cm^{-1} with considerable decrease in intensity, suggesting coordination through oxygen atom of pyrimidone ring C=O group.

The strong to medium intense bands observed in the region $1230\text{-}1205\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to C-O-C stretch (furan ring) in the free ligand²². These bands show considerable red shift suggesting the involvement of furan ring oxygen atom in bond formation with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions, whereas these bands do not show any perturbation or show slight blue shift in Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes suggesting non-involvement of furan ring oxygen atom in coordination. The coordination of furan ring oxygen with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes is further supported by the appearance of new non-ligand bands in the far-infrared region at 530 , 555 and 510 cm^{-1} , respectively assignable to M-O stretch (furan oxygen)²³. In all the complexes the new bands observed in the region $380\text{-}335\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to M-O stretch (carbonyl oxygen)²⁴. The non-ligand bands observed in the regions $320\text{-}300$ and $250\text{-}225\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are ascribed to terminal and bridging M-Cl stretch, respectively^{25,26} in all the complexes in view of their halogen bridged polymeric nature.

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References

1. S. B. MAHAJAN, Y. S. AGASIMUNDIN, R. O. KANTA and R. SRSHAYYAN, *J. Karnatak Univ. Sci.*, 1978, **23**, 120.
2. S. B. KADIN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, **15**, 551.
3. R. RAJNA and M. L. DHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 673.
4. H. LIPPAMA, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, **66**, 33240.
5. A. C. HIREMATH, N. V. HUGGI and M. B. HALLI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 607.
6. S. S. SANGAPURE and Y. S. AGASIMUNDIN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, **14**, 6886.
7. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
8. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1972.
9. A. W. MCLELLAN and G. A. MELSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **137**; A. K. RANA and J. R. SHAH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 177.
10. N. K. DATTA and N. C. CHAKRDER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 393; N. RAMA RAO, D. S. RAO and M. C. GANORKAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 839.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
12. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962; B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1967.
13. E. J. DUFF and M. N. HUGHES, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1968, 2144.
14. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1965.
15. K. C. PATEL and D. E. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 673.
16. M. S. PATIL, R. P. PATIL and J. R. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 120.
17. G. A. AGAMBAR and K. G. ORREL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 897.
18. M. M. MOSTAFA, S. M. HASSAN and G. M. IBRAHIM, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 285; N. SAHA and K. M. DATTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 940.
19. B. SINGH, P. L. MAURYA, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 29.
20. W. KLEMPER, M. W. CROWYN, A. H. MAKI and G. C. PIMENTEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5846.
21. H. CULBERTSON, J. C. DECIUS and V. E. CHRISTENSEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 4834.
22. K. U. JOSEPH and V. V. SOMAYAJULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 505.
23. P. R. SHUKLA and V. K. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 7; P. R. SHUKLA and R. TARRU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 252.
24. C. P. PRABHAKARAN and C. C. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3316.
25. P. BISCARNI, L. FUSINA, G. D. NIVELLINI, A. MANGIA and G. PRELIZZI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1974, 1846.
26. D. DEFILIPPO, A. LAI, E. R. TROGH, G. VERANI and C. PRETI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 73.